

Experiential Learning in the Japanese Classroom: A Framework Based on Kolb's Model

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Abstract

Japan's English education system remains heavily reliant on rote memorization, grammar translation, and teacher-centered instruction, despite official guidelines advocating communicative competence. This paper critiques the structural rigidity of typical Japanese ESL classrooms and proposes a shift toward experiential learning grounded in Kolb's cycle of concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. Using case studies and lesson redesigns, the paper demonstrates how immersive, context-rich experiences can better engage students, improve retention, and foster authentic language use. The implications extend beyond language acquisition, calling for a pedagogical culture shift rooted in autonomy, creativity, and risk-taking.

Keywords: Constructivist approaches, Applied linguistics, Learner autonomy, Educational policy reform

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Around the world, English has become the de-facto language in business and academics. This is a reality that Japan has been struggling with for quite some time. For example, recently the Japanese retail clothing outlet and manufacturer Uniqlo has decided to make the company's official internal language English meaning that a large amount of correspondence as well as meetings will not be conducted in Japanese. Other Japanese firms may soon follow Uniqlo's lead (<http://www.asahi.com/english/TKY201007090517.html>). Whether the area of research is computer science, physics, psychology, education, or commerce, a majority of the most prestigious international journals require submissions to be written in English, leaving those who have not had the motivation or opportunity to develop a sufficient level of linguistic proficiency at a grave disadvantage. However, this problem does not just affect individuals; in combination with the rapidly aging population, low birthrate, and shrinking tax base, low English ability could diminish Japan's ability to compete globally.

In this paper, first the teaching methodology being used in Japanese junior high schools and high schools will be introduced. Next, using Kolb's theory of experiential learning, I will provide a framework for changing English classes that are currently dominated by direct instruction and rote memorization into experiential learning opportunities.

Traditionally, English education in Japan has focused on reading, and grammar with little emphasis placed on listening, speaking, or composition. Largely, this material is covered using a combination direct learning methods and rote memorization (introduction of grammar topic and vocabulary, listening and repeating after the teacher or CD player, drilling while giving answers

individually or in unison, and writing practice). For example, a typical lesson to review or introduce basic punctuation, capitalization, vocabulary, and spelling, the plan for a 45-50 minute class would be as follows:

1. Have the students study the words from the previous lesson for a few minutes then take a short quiz. Usually, the words are given in Japanese and students translate them into English. When finished, students exchange papers with the person sitting next to them and score each other's work.
2. Flashcards are used to review or introduce new vocabulary. Students are drilled one at a time or are prompted to answer simultaneously.
3. The teacher gives a lecture indicating the important points, perhaps more new words, and grammar points. Cultural notes from America or other English-speaking countries may be included. All explanations are in Japanese.
4. The students take out their grammar workbooks and practice until the end of class. The teacher walks around the room correcting mistakes and helping students who did not understand something presented in the lesson.

According to the Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology (MEXT), the aim of the English curriculum is to shift from lecture-style classes and promote "smooth communication" which is defined as being able to communicate proactively and confidently while being culturally sensitive (2011, p.4); however, after an average of six years using these methods, most students still have great difficulty with basic daily exchanges in English. The reason this is so is quite easy to see; besides a few pictures in the textbook and the bromides about the importance of English, the language is almost completely de-contextualized.

Listening and speaking are neglected and students are robbed of the opportunity to pick up new words in context because everything is conducted in Japanese or immediately translated. A new approach is needed.

Based on the work of John Dewey and Kurt Levin, David Kolb's experiential learning methodology is based on the belief that "learning is the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience." Unlike proponents of direct instruction who believe knowledge is outside of the learner and must be "captured" and understood, proponents of experiential learning believe that learning is continuously being created and recreated (Kolb, 1984). Learning is not just passively absorbing information to later be recalled for an exam or complete a task. It is a process, with no end, but may change with context. Although there are much more detailed diagrams and explanations, Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle has four basic steps: concrete experience (CE), reflective observation (RO), abstract conceptualization (AC), and active experimentation (AE) (Friedman, Watts, Croston, & Durkin, 2002).

Kolb also observed that people show a preference for certain steps in the Learning Cycle and could be divided into four different learning styles: assimilators, who learn better when presented with sound logical theories to consider; convergers, who learn better when provided with practical applications of concepts and theories; accommodators, who learn better when provided with "hands-on" experiences; and divergers, who learn better when allowed to observe and collect a wide range of information (www.learning-theories.com/experiential-learning-kolb.html).

In the lesson plan above, assimilators are the only learning style the teacher has given any consideration. There is no engagement or interactivity. Even information retention, something

that direct instruction can do well, is crippled by allowing the students review the words immediately before the test. Any child with a descent short-term memory should have no problems passing and what was “studied” will be soon forgotten.

To make the lesson more experiential, I propose the following:

1. Give students a list of words in Japanese for homework. The students then look up the words using a dictionary and then make their own word cards. The parents or teachers should check the cards to make sure they are correct. After the students have done greetings, the quizzes are passed out immediately. The teacher writes the answers on the board, the students exchange quizzes and score them (CE, RO, AC).
2. The teacher models the pronunciation, accent, and intonation for the old and new vocabulary words without showing the flashcards. The teacher then asks the students what the words mean in Japanese. The only Japanese spoken at this point should be the meanings of the vocabulary. All other talk should be in English (AC, AE).
3. Because teaching grammar is necessary from time to time, the explanation should be structured in a way that allows students to understand even with their limited vocabulary. Students should already know terms such as verb, noun, or tense names because they would have already been introduced and used in every class. To introduce cultural components, the internet provides nearly limitless possibilities all in authentic English. Many schools have electronic blackboards with internet connections that go unused because many teachers do not understand the technology (AE, CE).
4. Finally, students can take out their grammar notebooks and do the exercises. Students can be given homework asking them to create a short dialogue, sentences, or a story using the

vocabulary and grammar learned in class. Students can use the conversations in the textbook and workbook as examples. Later, a game can be introduced giving students to use their new skills “live,” but in an environment where even making mistakes is fun (CE, RO, AC, AE).

Although these changes to make lessons more student-centered would be beneficial, there are numerous hurdles. Many of the English teacher's levels are quite low because they have limited experience abroad. It is often hard for them to catch mistakes that fall outside of their study or experiences. So often, a junior high school teacher's English level will remain low because it was not so high to begin with. MEXT wanted all English teachers to have a TOEIC score of at least 730; however, as of 2011, only 24% of junior high school teachers and 49% of high school teachers have attained that score (2011, p.11). Considering this, direct instruction is over utilized because it covers the teacher's gaps in knowledge. This avoids embarrassment for teachers and most likely helps to inflate English test scores, but ultimately shortchanges the students.

References

- Friedman, A., Watts, D., Croston, J., & Durkin, C. (2002) Evaluating online CPD using educational criteria derived from the experiential learning cycle. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 33(4), 367-78.
- Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology (2011). Five proposals and specific measures for developing proficiency in english for international communication. Retrieved from http://www.mext.go.jp/component/english/_icsFiles/afieldfile/2012/04/11/1319707_1_1.pdf
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: experience as the source of learning and development*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall.
- Learning Theories Knowledgebase (2012, May). Experiential learning (Kolb) at Learning-Theories.com. Retrieved from <http://www.learning-theories.com/experiential-learning-kolb.html>
- Nannichi, K., (2010) Uniqlo to use English as official language in 2012. Asahi Shimbun. Retrieved from <http://www.asahi.com/english/TKY201007090517.html>

Appendix

Allen, A.A., (1993) Teaching American culture: an independent project for an intermediate oral language class. Retrieved from <http://www.eric.ed.gov/PDFS/ED370371.pdf>

Field, R.(n.d.) John Dewey. *The Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Northwest Missouri State University UTM.edu - The University of Tennessee at Martin Retrieved from <http://www.iep.utm.edu/dewey/>

Lee, C., (2012). Revisiting why incompetents think they're awesome. Arstechnica Scientific Method/Science and Exploration. Retrived from http://arstechnica.com/science/2012/05/revisiting-why-incompetents-think-theyre-awesome
/2/

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